

D7.4

Pollution risk map

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Deliverable 7.4 Pollution risk map

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Interactive Pollution Risk Maps (html): <https://zenodo.org/records/15321503>

Interactive Pollution Risk Maps (html): <https://soilolive.eu/results/deliverable-7-4/>

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Executive Summary

This report corresponds to Work Package 7 of the Soil O-Live project and focuses on data derived from Task 2.1, which involved the assessment of pesticides and copper in olive grove soils. The study encompasses 52 farms located across five Mediterranean countries—Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy, and Greece—representing a wide range of soil management practices. Through this analysis, the project seeks to assess the current state of conservation of Mediterranean olive groves and to better understand how different management strategies affect soil health.

Pollution maps

1. Copper


```

model<- lm(Cu ~ AGE + MANAGEMENT + COUNTRY, data= soil_data)
anova(model)

## Analysis of Variance Table

##

## Response: Cu

##      Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value  Pr(>F)
## AGE      1  51473   51473  9.7605 0.003189 **
## MANAGEMENT 2   5284    2642  0.5010 0.609418
## COUNTRY   4  24394    6099  1.1564 0.343307
## Residuals 43 226765    5274

## ---

## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

The copper map is the result of the historical accumulation of copper in the soil, as observed in the model. Although copper is applied to the leaves, these compounds reach the soil where they

become immobilized. Over many years, they accumulate in the soil, thus being a source of contamination and potentially continuing to act as fungicides.

This relationship becomes more evident under organic management, where olive groves are older and soil conservation practices are applied. Improved soil structure is promoted by higher levels of organic matter and the maintenance of vegetation cover, which reduces erosion and progressively increases copper accumulation.

2. Glyphosate and AMPA

This relationship becomes more evident under organic management, where olive groves are older and soil conservation practices are applied. Improved soil structure is promoted by higher levels of organic matter and the maintenance of vegetation cover, which reduces erosion and progressively increases copper accumulation.

At the geographical level, similar trends were observed for both glyphosate and AMPA, with notably high levels detected in intensified olives groves in Spain and Portugal, while lower concentrations were found in other countries and management. In contrast to intensive olive groves, organic orchards have zero or almost zero values due to the ban on the use of these substances.

3. Other herbicides

A similar pattern was observed for other herbicides in use, both in terms of countries and management practices. Portugal showed significantly higher concentrations, likely due to the fact that most of the sampled farms in this country were intensified (3 out of 5).

4. Fungicides

Although individually the different fungicide compounds are below the legal limits (Deliverable 6.10), when we group these compounds by their purpose, we find high values in organic olive groves and in some conventional ones, which could have a significant impact on the abundance of fungal communities.

5. Insecticides

Similarly, to fungicides, the accumulation of all groups of insecticides could negatively impact the soil’s macro-, meso-, and microfauna. In particular, it is important to highlight the levels found in organic farms in Spain and Italy compared to other countries and treatments.

Conclusions

This study highlights that soil management practices in Mediterranean olive groves significantly influence the accumulation of contaminants such as copper, herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides. Copper has historically accumulated in the soil, especially in older organic orchards, where improved soil conservation practices. While glyphosate and its metabolite AMPA showed high concentrations in intensified farms in Spain and Portugal, organic farms consistently exhibited minimal or zero levels. Similarly, other herbicides were more prevalent in intensified systems, particularly in Portugal.

Although individual pesticide compounds remained below legal thresholds, their combined presence—especially fungicides and insecticides—raises concerns about potential negative impacts on soil fungal communities and soil fauna. Notably, elevated levels of these compounds were also found in some organic farms in Spain and Italy, suggesting possible historical residues, cross-contamination, or deviations from organic management practices.